

An Assessment of Biographical Account of Some Selected Zabarmawa Personalities in Gusau Metropolis

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Abstract

This paper provides biographical account of some selected Zabarma personalities in Gusau metropolis. The individual Zabarma discussed in this paper represents the activities of the mainstream of the Zabarma living in Gusau from 1930-2000. The paper also provides an explanation on how some of these migrant occupied prominent positions through hard work and concerted effort in promoting socio-economic values in the mainstream society of Gusau. This was achieved either for their economic importance or other services rendered to the host community. The tool for data collection of this study include interview with schedule key informants.

Keywords: *Biographical Account, Zabarmawa, Personalities, Gusau Metropolis, socio-economic.*

Introduction

This paper provides biographical account of some selected Zabarma personalities. The individual Zabarma identified and discussed in this paper represents the activities of the mainstream of the Zabarma living in Gusau from 1930-2000. This paper provides an explanation on how some of these migrant occupied prominent positions through hard work and concerted effort in promoting socio-economic values in the mainstream society of Gusau. This was achieved either for their economic importance or other services rendered to the host community. The paper also selects ten prominent Zabarma personalities in Gusau.

Alhaji Attahiru Baciri

Baciri popularly known as Baciri Sabon Garin Zabarma - Village Head he is one of the prominent Zabarma in Gusau Town. He was born in September 1st, 1958 at Roman Catholic Hospital, Tudun Wada Area, Gusau. He was the first son of Malam Muhammad Bashir a former and first Village Head of Zabarma in Gusau. His educational career started when he was four (4), under the tutelage of his first Qur'anic teacher named Malam Juri a Fulani by origin. He was later transferred to another Quranic school at old prison under the mentorship of Malam Sule Mai Bulala (Hausa by origin) where he acquired necessary skills for reciting the holy Qur'an and admitted into secular education in the year 1964. He went to Tudun Wada Primary School and graduated in 1971 from where he moved to Government Secondary School Gusau (now Government Science Secondary School Gusau) and graduated in July, 1976.¹

After secondary school education, he was employed as Produced Inspector (PI) at the Ministry of Agriculture, Sokoto, in the year 1976. He attended different seminars and workshops among which were: "Food Storage Technology" at Nigeria Produced Research Institute Kano in 1982 and several local trainings and workshops organized by the Ministry of Agric Sokoto. In the year 1990, Baciri went to College of Agriculture Zuru for his National Diploma in Agricultural Mechanization where he graduated in 1992. He went to Federal College of Education Gusau (F.C. E.T Gusau) and obtained Diploma in Computer Science in 2005. He retired as Nigeria Agric Produced Store Officer in 2003. He is married with three wives two from Hausa origin, one from Zabarma origin. He has twenty-three children. He is now a Village Head residing in Anguwar Zabarma Tudun Wada Gusau. There are ten ward heads under him as mentioned in

¹ Oral Interview with Attahiru Baciri 63 years, Zabarma Village Head, at his palace, Anguwar Zabarma Gusau, 18-01-2021.

chapter two. He also engaged in buying and selling of farm produce. At the time of conducting this research, he provides consultancy services on farm products storage to farmers of the metropolis.

In terms of Baciri's contribution, he contributed significantly to the social, economic and political development of Gusau metropolis. He secured admission to both Zabarmawa and Hausawa youths within and outside the metropolis. He also negotiates and reconciles cases that affected Zabarmawa and their host community. This greatly helped and cemented inter-ethnic relations in the metropolis.

Alhaji Ibrahim Ahmad Zabarma

Alhaji Ibrahim Ahmad is another prominent Zabarma migrant in Gusau metropolis. He was born on 2nd February, 1968 in Tudun Wada, Gusau. He started his educational career in 1971 under his father named Malam Amadu Dosso. Afterwards, he memorized the holy Qur'an. After memorization of the Qur'an before he was admitted into Tudun Wada Primary School, from 1973 to 1978. He then proceeded to Government Teachers College, Chafe in 1979 and later Government Secondary School Gusau. He graduated in June 1983. He proceeded to Advanced Teachers Collage, Maru for preliminary studies and obtained Nigerian Certificate in Education (N.C. E) in 1985. He later proceeded to Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and studied Civil Law where he graduated in the year 1987.

However, after his educational career he started business. He also went to Abeokuta Olak Company in 1988 as Sales and Marketing Manager. He left the company after spending a year in Lagos at Mansin & Co. 72 Allen Avenue Ikeja as Sales Representative, representing Sokoto state that is Supply Officer between Lagos and Sokoto. He left for the Bank of the North in Kano as staff in 1989. He spent only six months at Kano before he was transferred to Sokoto branch. After about nine months of service in Sokoto, he was transferred to Birnin Kebbi where he spent nine years. He was posted to Abuja headquarters of the same bank (Bank of the North), where he spent two years and due to the bank liquidation, he finally disengaged from service in 1998.

Following his disengagement from private service in 1998, Alhaji Ibrahim embarked into business where he was buying and selling textile materials and electronics in Kaduna, Kano and Gusau respectively. He occupied the position of wholesaler in these businesses. In 2005, Alhaji Ibrahim Ahmad Zabarma decided to establish a well standard construction company and a borehole drilling company. He owned Zabarma Drilling and Construction Company. In addition to the establishment of this company, he operates his business in textile materials and electronics. He is also a major supplier of grains to different companies and governmental organizations. He is currently the Chairman of Zabarkanu Bankanu Association of Nigeria Zamfara, State Chapter. A socio-cultural association of Zabarma established in the year 2000 and registered in 2004 by some concerned Zabarma origins with the aim of promoting socio-cultural and economic well-being of all members in the metropolis. According to Ibrahim,²this association was basically established in order to extend relationship among Zabarma in Gusau metropolis. Some of the objectives of the association are:

- i. To enhance Zabarma socio-cultural relations among members, that is to revive their language and other Zabarma cultural activities in the metropolis.
- ii. To remove all barriers among the Zabarma migrants as well as promote unity. Ibrahim asserts that Zabarma in Gusau are classified into two: first, there are original inhabitants who considered themselves as indigenes and part of Gusau community and the second are migrated from Niger Republic to Gusau for one reason or another. The latter are still migrating to Gusau for economic purpose. In fact, Gusau became Zabarma transition centre.³
- iii. To identify themselves as a community for other entitlements
- iv. To help one another in different ramification of life as a community. Zabarma wanted to understand their members in the metropolis for future planning including giving out assisting to members.
- v. To use the association as a medium for sensitization among members for anything related Alhaji Ibrahim Ahmed is happily married with one wife and six children comprising three boys and three girls.

Ahmed Zabarma contributed significantly contributed in the unification of all Zabarmawa of Gusau metropolis. In fact, he facilitated a cordial relationship between the Zabarma and host communit including the promotion of inter-marriages in Gusau. In addition, he established a drilling company for social development of the people of the metropolis. He drilled water boreholes to many households at a subsidized rate in the metropolis.

Mai Anguwa Adamu Alfari

Malam Adamu was born in 1919 in Falwal Village in Dosso State of Niger Republic. He left Niger Republic for two reasons drought and famine at former place of destination and looking for socio-economic opportunity in northern

² This information was only not obtained from Alhaji Ibrahim but from many informants such as Mai Anguwa Alfari, Malam Hinsu, Hussaini Yahaya Ishaqa, and Alhaji Muhammad Ahmad all and many more mostly interviewed already Zabarma migrants in Gusau metropolis.

³ Oral Interview with Alhaji Ibrahim Ahmad Zabarma, 53 years, Business man, at his Residence, Tudun Wada, Gusau, on 16-04- 2021.

Nigeria. However, before he left home (Niger), he was enrolled into western education. But he dropped out after a year and continued with Islamic education. In 1930, his early literacy helped him to started working with a leather company, after about three years he left to Nigeria (Gusau) through the influence of Auta Gareji (a prominent rail line worker among Zabarma).⁴ More so, there was an assertion made by the then Islamic scholars (*Malamai*) who were considered as saints among Zabarma that there will be a time of hunger, as a result of a plague and diseases in the area. A considerable number of Zabarma left their permanent homes to different places in northern Nigeria, Gusau included. Alfari left immediately after he received the message. He went to Sokoto and engaged in buying and selling of leather works materials in 1934. After a year he decided to move to Gusau under the pressure of his friend named Auta. At Gusau, Alfari started work as food vendor in a leather industry owned by John Holt, he became one of the buyers within the environs. In 1949 Alfari was employed into the Nigerian Army. He left Kano and moved to Azare town in 1950. In the year 1953, Alfari was advised by his family to marry second wife whom was from his relatives. She (the second wife) resided in Gusau. After the wedding, she was taken to Azare town where he worked. He also married third wife at Biu town (now in Yobe state). He came back to Gusau in 1977 as a retired army. At Gusau, Alfari decided to embark on a business where he rented Gusau Games Club Hotel and Restaurant. In 1982 he opened up another Restaurant at Kauran Namoda town and became a major food contractor at Orphanage Home Gusau. He was married with four wives and twenty-five children. Alfari is one of the prominents Zabarma Ward Head in Tudu Wada Gusau.

In terms of Alfari's contribution, he contributed in the dissemination of local history of Zabarmawa migrants in Gusau. In fact, Zabarmawa referred students and researchers to him to get relevant information on the history of Zabarmawa community in Gusau and Zamfara state as whole. As a retired soldier, he facilitated the recruitment of substantial number of Zabarmawa into the Nigerian Army. Some of these Zabaramawa have risen to various ranks and positions in the service.

Malam Yahaya Hussaini Ishaq (Tawai)

Yahaya Hussaini Ishaq is another prominent Zabarma migrant in Gusau town. His father Malam Ishaq came to Gusau town in 1950s. Malam Hussaini was born on 15th January, 1956 at Sabon Fegi area of Gusau town. He started his early education at Sabon Fegi with Malam Maisaje, a local Arabic teacher. Later, he moved to Islamiyyah Isdilahuddeen at Anguwar Toka Gusau in 1969-1972. He went to Nizzamiyyah Primary School where he obtained Primary School Certificate in 1973. Malam Hussain proceeded to Sultan Abubakar College Sokoto where he obtained Higher Islamic School Certificate in 1977.

As a result, he was employed as primary school teacher in Local Government Education Authority (LGEA) Kauran Namoda town. He was first posted to Modomawa Primary School to teach Arabic in 1977-1978. In 1978, following the establishment of Universal Primary Education Commission, (U.P.E) he was posted as pioneer Head Master at Saken Kade town in the present day Kebbi state. In 1979, he went back to College of Education Sokoto (now SSCOE) to further his educational career where he obtained Nigeria Certificate of Education (NCE) in Arabic Medium in 1983. He later went to Benue state for one-year National Youth Service Corps (N.Y.S.C). After his graduation, he was re-engaged into Civil Service Commission Sokoto as a fresh public servant in 1984. After which he was posted to teach Arabic in Junior Secondary School Yankuzo - Tsafe Local Government Area of Zamfara state up till 1986. He gained admission into Bayero University Kano and completed his degree programme in 1990. After his graduation, he was transferred to Government Arabic Secondary School, Zurmi up to the year 2001. Due to his hard work, he was appointed as Principal Inspector of Education (P.I.E), Zamfara State Arabic and Islamic Education Board Gusau. After couple of years, he was promoted to the rank of Deputy Director Inspectorate up to the year 2003. In the year 2004 – 2006, he was appointed as Coordinator Examinations to the board. He was transferred to Institute of Arabic and Islamic Studies, Moriki as Principal from 2006 to 2011. He was later transferred to Arabic and Islamic Education Board, Gusau as Deputy Director Inspectorate up to 2016 where he finally retired from state service.

Malam Hussaini was combining his government job with the business of selling Kerosene especially within the period of 1990 and 2001. Also, when he was principal at G.A.S.S Zurmi, he usually bought five drums of Kerosene and two of palm Oil from Gusau whenever he was returning from the weekend. He sold kerosene and palm oil to the members of staff and other members of the community. Apart from being him a public servant, he supplied the above-mentioned products to farmers as well as engaged in the cultivation of variety of food and cash crops.⁵

After his retirement, he continued pursuing his Arabic and Islamic knowledge and teaching career where he established an Islamic school Madrasatil Intisharu Ulumuddeen Al-Islamiyyah (School for Spreading Islamic Knowledge) at Anguwar Gwaza Housing Estate, Gusau. He is currently the Head Teacher in the said school. He is married with four

⁴Autu Gareji was an old rail line worker in Nigeria. He left Niger Republic since his childhood. As a friend in school he sent to Alfari for the growing opportunities in Nigeria.

⁵ Oral Interview with Malam Yahaya Hussain (Tawai) ,63 Years, a Retired Civil Servant in Gusau, at his Residence Anguwar Gwaza Housing Estate Gusau. 6-04- 2021

wives and twenty-seven children comprising thirteen boys and fourteen girls among them is Murtala Yahaya who is working with the state Ministry of Education, Gusau and Shafa'atu Yahaya, working with the Arabic and Islamic Education Board, Gusau.

In terms of Ishaq's contribution, he facilitated the employment of twenty-seven Zabarmawa and Hausawa to different positions at Arabic and Islamic Education Board, Zamfara state. He also established Islamic model school-Madarasatul Hizbulrahim Talamiyatul Shiek Khalid Ibrahim at Janyau Fulani Area, Gusau.

Alhaji Abdurrazaq Adamu Zabarma

Abdulrazaq Adamu Zabarma is also among the prominent Zabarma migrants in Gusau metropolis. He was born in 1951 at Anguwar Zabarma Gusau. His father Malam Adamu Bazabarme was from Dosso state of Niger Republic. He came to Gusau around 1930s for Islamic scholarship. He first resided at Kanwuri area in Gusau. After a while, he was given a place to reside at Tankin Ruwa in Sabon Gari area and later moved to Anguwar Zabarma Tudun Wada Gusau.

Abdurrazaq started his early education under his father named Malam Adamu. Later, he was admitted into Kanwuri Junior Primary School in 1956. After his graduation, he went to Senior Primary School Kotorkoshi and graduated in 1965. Again, he went to Nagarta College Sokoto (now Government College Sokoto) up till 1969. He sat for High School Certificate and sat for Common Wealth Examination between 1969 and 1971. He worked temporarily with Universal Primary Education for one year and nine months. He went to Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria where he studied B. A. Education History; and graduated in 1977. He was posted to Asaba (now Delta State) for one-year National mandatory service (NYSC).⁶

In terms of experience, he joined the service at College of Education Sokoto in 1978 as Assistant lecturer in the Department of Education up to 1981. He went to United States of America (U.S.A), Ohio University for Master's Degree where he studied Education Psychology, Special Life on Human Relations (Guidance and Counseling). He graduated in 1982 and came back to College of Education Sokoto, Education Department. He was appointed as coordinator of B. Ed. Degree Programme. In 1984, he went to Sokoto state Polytechnic as Counseling Officer up to 1986. He became the Dean, School of Education in same school from 1986 to 1988. He was the Deputy Provost from 1988 to 1989 and was the Acting Provost in 1991. He finally became Provost in 1996. When Zamfara state was created he went back to Gusau as the first Executive Secretary Zamfara State Teachers Service Board, Gusau. He was appointed as Permanent Secretary, Cabinet Affairs and General Services in 2006 by the then Yariman Bakura Administration. He retired as permanent secretary in 2011. Before his retirement, he was a member of different associations both national and local: Member, Counseling Association of Nigeria, Curriculum Association of Nigeria, Association of Education Psychologist and Zabarkanu Bankanu Association, Zamfara state⁷ among others. He is married with wives one from Zabarma and another from Hausa and sixteen children comprising ten boys and six girls, among them are Abdurrahman Abdurrazaq Zabarma who is a computer scientist, Sadiq Abdurrazaq and Nasir Abdurrazaq who are both lecturers at Federal College of Education Technical (F.C.E.T), Gusau just to mention a few. He is currently a farmer and holding different traditional titles. (Danburan Tudun Wada, Magayakin Low cost, Mai Anguwar Mill Goma). He is living in Tudun Wada Low Cost Housing Estate, Gusau.

In terms of Adamu's contribution, he has contributed to the social and economic development of Gusau metropolis. Before his appointment as Permanent Secretary, he has secured admission to a substantial number of both Zabarmawa and Hausawa youth in the metropolis. He secured them admission at Shehu Shagari College of Education (SSCOE), Sokoto and College of Administration-Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic, Sokoto. Again, he was part of the Zabarmawa that led the foundation of a consolidated Zabarmawa forum in 1999. He was the pioneer Zabarma Chairman of Zamfara State Teachers' Service Board, Gusau. Before he left the Board, he employed thirty-five Zabarmawa and Hausawa as teaching and non-teaching staff.

Malam Ahmadu Na Malam Yakubu (Alfazazi)

He is one of the reputed Zabarma scholars in Sabon Fegi Zawiyya Babba also popularly known as Zawiyyar Malam Yakubu Bazabarme. He was born in 1958 at Dogon Dutse of Dosso state in Niger Republic.⁸ His father Malam Yakubu was a robbing scholar from Dogon Dutse Dosso state of Niger Republic who came to Gusau in 1950s. He met his cousin Malam Khalidu Na Malam Babba (a re-known scholar and also a cassette dealer) at Gusau. In 1964, Alfazazi went to

⁶ Oral Interview with Abdurrazaq Adamu Zabarma, 61 years, Retired Permanent Secretary, at his residence Tudun Wada Housing Estate Gusau, 16- 10- 2020

⁷ The association which he stated was established in order to assist the younger generation among Zabarma to have access to education and other privileges that may difficult to have access to.

⁸ Oral Interview with Malam Ahmadu Malam Yakubu (Alfazazi), 63years, An Islamic Scholar, at his Residence Zawiyyar Malam Yakubu Bazabarme, Sabon Fegi Gusau, 22- 04- 2021.

Matankari village in Kebbi state and studied different books in Islamic theology, *Fiqh* and other different area of learning under the tutelage of Malam Adamu Bagobiri. After about ten years, he came back to Gusau and continued his educational pursuance under his father. He was introduced to the Cassette business after his arrival at Gusau by Malam Khalid Na Malam Babba his cousin. Alfazazi spent eight years in this business, his main source was his cousin Malam Khalid in Gusau, Alhaji Gado, Alhaji Suja all of Zabarma origin and Alhaji Nuhu Hausa of origin from Kano. In 1980s, he started business in blouse in which he spent three years. After the demise of his father, he can no longer continue with the business as he shoulders all his father's responsibilities. He continued running the school (Zawiyah) affair. The school is one among the oldest of its kind in Gusau metropolis. According to the informant, he continued visiting his father's colleagues to further his learning (Islamic) within and outside Gusau metropolis. Malam Alfazazi has only one wife from Zabarma origin and seven children comprising two boys and five girls. According to him the school is one of the Zabarma famous schools in the metropolis. The school graduated many students who currently owned their schools as prominent scholars among Zabarma community. Among them are Malam Ishaq Tudun Faila in Gusau, Malam Mikaila Tudun Kosau, Malam Salahu Bazabarme Janyau area Gusau and Malam Hussaini Matankari in Dogon Dutse, Dosso State Niger Republic a reknown scholar who studied under Malam Yakubu at Gusau and left for Niger.

Abdullahi Attahiru Zabarma Gusau

Abdullah Attahiru is another successful Zabarma migrant in Gusau. He was born in 3rd August, 1958 at Anguwar Zabarma Tudun Wada Gusau. He started his educational carrier from 1962 when he was taken to his first teacher Malam Haruna Jori, where he studied the basic Arabic alphabets and words until when he was literate with the Arabic and be conversant with reading the glorious Qur'an. In 1969, Abdullahi was admitted into secular school: Sudan Interior Mission Primary School (S I M) and graduated in 1973. He later secured admission with the Federal Government College Port Harcourt which he could not go because of the fear his parent had considering the distance. He spent one year selling Kola nuts. He took another common entrance examination and admitted to Sokoto Teachers College (S.T.C) Sokoto and graduated in 1979.⁹ He started teaching at Samaru Primary School within just a year and moved to College of Education, Sokoto from 1980 to 1983. After he graduated, he went to Oyo state for one-year compulsory National Youth Service Corps (NYSC).

In 1984, he took a fresh appointment with Sokoto State Civil Service Commission (C.S.C) and posted to Junior Secondary School (JSS) Kasuwar Daji to teach. After a year, Attahiru Zabarma was appointed acting Vice Principal of the same school up till 1987 when he was transferred to Government Secondary School, Gusau (GSS Gusau) to teach History. After spending about three years, Attahiru Zabarma proceeded to University of Sokoto, now Usmanu Danfodiyo Sokoto (UDUS) and graduated in 1994. He was appointed Deputy Education Secretary, Local Government Education Authority (LGEA) Gusau in the same year. He was transferred to Tsafe and Gusau respectively. Attahiru became Acting Education Secretary, Gusau Local Government Education Authority in the year 2007. Later, he was confirmed as Education Secretary (ES) and posted to Local Government Education Authority (LGEA) Bungudu in 2008. He was transferred to Talata Mafara and Gusau respectively up to 2013. And later, he was asked to handover to their second in command and moved to mother Ministry as Deputy Director, Higher and Teacher Education up to 2015, when he was promoted as Director, Higher and Teacher Education Zamfara State Ministry of Education, Gusau. Attahiru maintained the position up to 25th November, 2018 when he retired and joined politics. He is currently a Special Adviser to His Excellency, the Executive Governor of Zamfara State. He is married with four wives and twenty-eight children comprising eleven boys and seventeen females.

In terms of Attahiru's contribution, he has contributed significantly to the development of Gusau metropolis. He encouraged Zabarmawa to embrace and enroll their wards to western education. As Education Secretary (E.S), he employed considerable number on the average Zabarmawa and Hausawa youths as teachers at Bungudu and Gusau Local Government Education Authority (LGEA), Zamfara state. Some of them have become Seniors Master II.

Alhaji Umar Baciri

Umar Baciri is another prominent among Zabarma migrants in Gusau metropolis. He was born in 1963 at Anguwar Zabarma Gusau. He started his education under his father where he studied basic Arabic words and alphabets and continued studying the Qur'an up to 1970 when he was admitted into Tudun Wada Primary School and graduated in the year 1976. He proceeded to Government Teachers College, Kaura Namoda and had Grade II Certificate in 1981.¹⁰ Baciri started working with Local Government Education Authority Gusau (LGEA) and posted to Rugar Buda Primary School Nahuche as a Teacher. He went to College of Administration Sokoto, where studied Store Keeper's Course from 1981 to

⁹ According to the informant, He was opportune to have access to modern education because of his Elder brother who was then a Branch Manager Bank of the North. According to him (Attahiru) his brother was ever ready to assist anyone with the interest to further his education most especially those from Zabarma origin.

¹⁰ Oral interview with Alhaji Umar Baciri Zabarma, 59 years, a politician, his residence opposite Zabarma Model primary school Tudun Wada Gusau, 30-04- 2021

1982. He later joined College of Administration Sokoto as Staff Store Officer. He continued his educational career with the College of Administration, Sokoto (C.A.S) under the same cadre Store Officer. In 1986, Baciri went to School of Management at State Polytechnic, Birnin Kebbi where studied Diploma in Purchase and Supply. He continued his service with the State Polytechnic Birnin Kebbi from 1989 to 1992. Following the creation of Kebbi state, he joined State Service in the then Sokoto state, and posted to Ministry of Works, Sokoto as Principal Store Officer. He was transferred to State Health Service Management Board Sokoto (SHSMB) in 1994. He later came back to Ministry of Works in the same year. With the creation of Zamfara state, Baciri was posted to Ministry of Finance and later Ministry of Education as Principal Store Officer in 1997. He worked as an Ad hock Staff in Sambo Secondary School, where he taught commercial subjects until he resigned in 1999.¹¹

He joined politics and was given political appointments. After wards he was assigned to chair the scrapped Petroleum Trust Fund (PTF) material (moveable and immoveable) disbursement committee and was the state representative in 2001.¹² In 2003, he was also appointed as Education Trust Fund (E T F) Desk Officer. He was transferred to Ministry of Agriculture as Principal Store Officer and later in 2006 to General Services and Cabinet Affairs as Chief Store Officer. In 2011 he worked with the Ministry of Works in the same position until his retirement in 2017. He later went back to politics and joined APC and was appointed as Zamfara Central APC Zonal coordinator up the level of Gubernatorial Election which unfortunately banned and declared null and void by the Supreme Court. He is currently one of the prominent politicians among Zabarma migrant community in Gusau metropolis.

Apart from politics, Baciri is currently into business. He usually built houses for rent and sometime sold the house depending on the demand. He was a member of different nongovernmental organization especially business organizations. He is a Member National Auction Society of Nigeria. Alhaji Umar is married with two wives, one from Zabarma and the other from Hausa. This clearly shows how intimate the two (Zabarma and the host) were in term of Inter-group relation. He has sixteen children comprising eight boys and eight girls among which are Jamilu Umar Baciri, a graduate in Accountancy from Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto (UDUS). Jamilu is currently working with Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) head office Abuja. Aliyu Umar Baciri a graduate from biochemistry Udu, Ahmad Umar Bacri Babangida a graduate from Economics department Ahmadu Bello University Zaria among others.

Malam Habibu Ahmad Jubril

Malam Habibu is a famous Islamic scholar in Gusau metropolis. He is one of the Zabarma migrants in Gusau metropolis. He was born in 1972 Anguwaar Yan Shanu Sokoto. He started his Qur'anic education under his mother Hauwau and became conversant with the Qur'anic alphabets and words through the effort of his mother. He later started studying small books of Fiqh with his father Malam Amadu Jubrila, a Zabarma Malam at Sokoto. With the knowledge he acquired from his father informally, he was able to secure admission in Sheikh Abubakar Mahmud Gummi Memorial School, Sokoto in 1987 (JIS I). He was able to finished both JIS and SIS in the year 1992 and posted to Bankanu Primary School, Sokoto as teacher up till 1993.¹³

Malam Habibu participated in Daura program at Kano sponsored by Saudi government. He was one of the successful and went to Jamiatil Islamiyya Madina (Kulliyyatul Qur'an). He came back in 1995 as drop out from the University for one or the other reason. He went to Yemai in the Republic of Niger and continued the search for knowledge. He was appointed Imam of a Jumu'at mosque (Ahlissunsh Wal Jama'a Yantaladus) at Yemai and a Head Teacher, Madrasatil Ahlissunsh Waljamaah at the same area. In 1998, Malam Habib was given another admission by his former University to continue with his studies not fresh student. He continued from where he stopped and graduated in 2000 year. He was taken to Riyadh city and got interviewed as Daai (a preacher) and posted to Yemai in Niger after a while also transferred to Nigeria to serve the same position by Saudi Embassy Abuja. Fortunately, he was posted to Zamfara (Gusau) to not only preach but as an agent to ensure Islamic development in all its ramifications.¹⁴

¹¹ He voluntarily joined Sambo secondary school as a teacher teaching subject like Commercial Accounting, Record keeping among others.

¹² Baciri was delegated by the state government to ensure the disbursement of Petroleum Trust Fund (PTF) materials which was done promptly and properly. The five men committee was set up under the leadership of Umar Baciri in this regard.

¹³ Oral Interview with Malam Habibu, 48 years, Islamic scholar and Imam Barakallahu Jumu'at Mosque, at his House Brakallahu Gusau, Zamfara State, 07- 05- 2021

¹⁴ As an agent, through him un specified number of mosque and Islamiyyah schools, boreholes within and outside Gusau metropolis were constructed and are still constructing. They are also organized different lectures and seminars and above all given sponsors to Islamic university Madiana through Daura program.

Malam Habib was not only scholar but also a businessman. He is currently selling roofing sheet and other building materials at Sabuwar Kasuwa Gusau. He was also a lecturer Department of Law Zamfara State College of Arts and Science (ZACAS), Gusau. He is teaching law of Inheritance.¹⁵ He is married with four wives two from Zabarma origin and another one from Fulfulde Niger and the last one from Hausa origin. He currently lives with twenty-seven children comprising thirteen boys and fourteen girls.

In terms of Habibu's contribution, he engaged in Islamic teaching of both Zabarmawa and host community within the metropolis. He also established Abu-Ubaida Centre for Islamic Propagation comprising three Islamiyya schools and a Jumma'at Mosque called Usman Ibn Afan Mosque at Barakallahu Area, Gusau metropolis.

Alhaji Adamu Abdullahi Maizinari

Alhaji Adamu is another successful Zabarma migrant in Gusau metropolis. He was born in 1944 at Bachakka (Bunza) Kebbi state of Nigeria. According to him his parents were from Dosso (Tullo Village). His father was a local Arabic teacher who moved from Dosso to Tullo village when he was twelve in search of farming land; he farmed so many farm products at Tullo until he married at the age of eighteen. He decided to move to Gusau but sojourned at Bachakka for robbing scholarship. He was appointed as Local Arabic Teacher in the 1960. According to Alhaji Adamu, he left his father and moved to Gusau in search of Islamic knowledge. He first lived with Malam Ibrahim Gangaren Sabon Fegi, Gusau (are known Hausa Islamic teacher of his own time). He started sold cassette (Audio) and later Rice, Beds and Mattresses up to 1975, when he visited his cousin in Coutonour, Benin Republic who was gold business, he took some valuable items to him. On his arrival, he was advised to start the business. He started by buying currency made with the gold some gold melted items. They usually smelted these products and sold as pure gold, they carry their product to Lagos for sale. After his pilgrimage in 1983 their major sources according to him were Maiduguri, Cotornour, Kebbi and Sokoto. The Yoruba people are the one already smelting the products (Jewelries, currency among others) to its pureness. Alhaji Adamu faced many challenges as a new gold buyer from the existing Yoruba gold buyers. One AbdulGaniyu and his allies from Yoruba origin continued to challenge him in the business but he withstood the challenge to the extent they became friends. As a friend, he cautioned his Yoruba allies to consider him as a colleague in the business. From 1979 to 1980s he collaborated with white men as their buyer. In 1994, he became an agent between the mining office Jos and the Paris Company Lagos. He was in charge of collecting any relevant papers and permits from the mining officer to a company or individual who intended to embark into mining activities. He usually went to the then Sultan of Sokoto to collect permission letters to the district heads of the affected areas where mining was going to take place. He collected permission letters through Sultan to District Head of Anka in order to embark into mining in Wuya, Gagare and Bungu villages of Anka Local government. According to him in those days they usually boarded Air plane from Kaduna to Lagos then to Cortonour and sold their products (gold) but they don't collect money from there until when they arrived Lagos. Alhaji Adamu Maizinari spent about thirty-nine years in the business but in 1994 he started showing interest on precious stones and he is now one of the major dealers of these stones in Zamfara. Alhaji Adamu is currently the chairman Zamfara state Gold Buyers and Sellers Union. He is married with three wives one from Zabarma and the other from Bachakka and one from Gusau town as well. He lives with twenty-two children comprising five girls and fifteen boys.

References

1. Oral Interview with Attahiru Baciri 63 years, Zabarma Village Head, at his palace, Anguwar Zabarma Gusau, 18-01-2021.
2. This information was only not obtained from Alhaji Ibrahim but from many informants such as Mai Anguwa Alfari, Malam Hussaini Yahaya Ishaqa, and Alhaji Muhammad Ahmad all and many more mostly interviewed already Zabarma migrants in Gusau metropolis.
3. Oral Interview with Alhaji Ibrahim Ahmad Zabarma, 53 years, Business man, at his Residence, Tudun Wada, Gusau, on 16-04- 2021.
4. Oral Interview with Malam Yahaya Hussain (Tawai) ,63 Years, a Retired Civil Servant in Gusau, at his Residence Anguwar Gwaza Housing Estate Gusau. 6-04- 2021
5. Oral Interview with Abdurrazaq Adamu Zabarma, 61 years, Retired Permanent Secretary, at his residence Tudun Wada Housing Estate Gusau, 16- 10- 2020
6. Oral Interview with Malam Ahmadu Malam Yakubu (Alfazazi), 63years, An Islamic Scholar, at his Residence Zawiyyar Malam Yakubu Bazabarme, Sabon Fegi Gusau, 22- 04- 2021.

¹⁵ Apart from lecturing Malam Habib as scholar wrote many books especially on Isamaic Theology. Example He wrote about thirty-five books on Aqidah (Islamic Theology) Tambihul Ulul Albab, (A Reminder for the Wise) and another one. The seven Important Messages to whoever need guidance and true Religion with Evidance from Qur'an and Hadith. He owned a Centre for Islamic teachings and revivalism at Barakallahu Gusau Zamfara state.

7. Oral interview with Abdullahi Attahiru Zabarma, 60 years, retired civil servant, at his residence Anguwar Zabarma, Tudun Wada, Gusau Town, 07-05-2021
8. Oral interview with Alhaji Umar Baciri Zabarma, 59 years, a politician, his residence opposite Zabarma Model primary school Tudun Wada Gusau, 30-04- 2021
9. Oral Interview with Malam Habibu Ahmad, 48 years, Islamic scholar and Imam Barakallahu Jumuat Mosque, at his House Brakallahu Gusau, Zamfara State, 07- 05- 2021
10. Oral interview with Adamu Abdullahi Maizinari, 71 years, Islamic Scholar, at his residence Sabon Fegi, Gusau Town, 08-05-2021